

**A NEW CONID (GASTROPODA: CONIDAE)
SPECIES FOUND IN SOMALIA**

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FERRARIO & BOZZETTI (La Conchiglia 258, 1991, p. 29) mentioned that the eighties were marked by a wealth of findings in the deep waters off Somalia, and that the present decade continues to follow suit, which appears to also include new species found in shallow waters as well. Among these, we have discovered a population of conid species, with characteristics more commonly occurring in the Caribbean region for its shape and size, which we are proposing hereunder as a new taxon:

Hermes (Magelliconus) lizarum sp. nov.

Description: Shell subcylindrical with a low, slightly stepped, conic spire and having a tan apex consisting of a double-whorled protoconch and 7 spiral whorls, surfaces of which are lightly incised with arcuate striae and sloping concavely, with the penultimate whorl forming a strongly keeled and angulate shoulder. The sides are completely flat down its elongate body whorl, which is irregularly incised with shallow transverse grooves, becoming more deeply indented towards the anterior end. The ground color is peach-pink with the body whorl having several patches of a lighter shade here and there or being encircled with interrupted rows of white and brown dots. The spire is similarly tinted but is decorated with a necklace of tiny brown spots completely encircling each whorl just below its rim. The aperture has parallel sides and is also colored peach-pink. Young specimens are seen in light brown coloration.

Type locality: Taken by shrimpers in deep water off Cape Guardafui, Somalia, Western Indian Ocean.

Holotype: 29.1 mm x 14.0 mm, deposited in the Musée d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva, under No. MHNG 16151.

Paratypes: No. 1 — 23.8 mm x 10.8 mm deposited in the Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde, Stuttgart (SMNS) with the Inv. N. ZI 8468

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No. 2 — 22.5 mm x 10.3 mm in the American Museum of Natural History, New York

No. 3 — 28.3 x 13.7 mm in coll. Gabriella Raybardi, Italy

No. 4 — 24.0 x 11.2 mm in coll. António Monteiro, Portugal

No. 5 — 21.3 x 10.0 mm in coll. António Nora, Portugal

No. 26.0 x 11.2 mm in coll. António Nova, Portugal.

Discussion: The new species compares closest in both shape and coloration to *C. aureonimbosus* PETUCH, 1987, Trawled off Florida Keys, except perhaps the latter has somewhat wider shoulders. Younger specimens however resemble *C. eversoni* PETUCH, 1987, found in Utila Island, Honduras, for its more cylindrical body whorl and lower flat spire. Certainly, nothing comes readily to mind from the Indo-Pacific region for making additional comparison. Two species from closer areas, belonging to genus *Hermes*, could be mentioned:

Hermes (*Fumiconus*) *dictator* (MELVILL, 1989) found in deep water from India to off South Western Thailand coasts, bears some resemblances in the general shape and coloration, but it has a taller, concavely conic spire on broader shoulder, attaining bigger size and very often showing an axially disposed pattern of irregular tan-brown flames superimposing the lighter ground color and rows of spots.

Hermes (*Fumiconus*) *traversianus* (E.A. SMITH, 1875) from the Gulf of Oman, northern Indian Ocean, has also a pattern of dotted rows similar to the new species, but its spire is taller, stepped and deeply concave, its body whorl being also differently sculptured.

Etymology: This new taxon is affectionately dedicated to the second author's wife and the first author's daughter, both having in common the same name.

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Hermes (*Magelliconus*) *lizarum*, n.sp.

Fig. 1 — Holotype, MHNG, Geneva. Dorsal, ventral view.

Fig. 2 — Paratype 2, Dorsal and ventral view.

Fig. 3 — Paratype 1, SMNS, Stuttgart. Dorsal and ventral view.

